

Does Social Competence, Emotional Intelligence, and Motivation, impact Employee Performance on Construction Companies?

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Abstract: Employee performance is very important and crucial to the influence that the company will get, especially for companies engaged in services, the quality and quantity of a company really requires good performance from its employees / human resources. Social competence, emotional intelligence, and work motivation are things that can affect the increase or decrease in employee performance. And this research uses quantitative research methods conducted at construction companies in Jakarta, Indonesia. Sample taken from 92 employees in construction companies in Jakarta, Indonesia. Data collection methods using primary data by distributing questionnaires. The result from data analysis by using structural equation modelling shows that social competence, emotional intelligence, and motivation has a positive impact to employee performance on construction companies in Jakarta, Indonesia.

Keywords: *Social competence, Emotional intelligence, Work motivation, and Employee performance, Construction Companies, Jakarta Indonesia*

I. Introduction

The progress of a company is not regardless of the Human Resources owned. Human resources take hold an important role in a company because they always play an active and dominant role in every company activity. Every good company that is engaged in service sector and industry always attempt to manage resource management human power in professional ways to improve employee performance. To improve performance, then the presence of employees who have social competence, emotional intelligence and work motivation is needed. In research conducted by Iskandar Agung (2014) To create a high level of human resources, employees must be competent good social because it is which is very important in improving employee performance. Social competence reflects the ability of employees to establish cooperative relationships and interact with others in work to achieve personal goals and organizational goals. Competence low social status of an employee to interact with each other work can have an impact on being difficult to achieve the goals of the organization due to the slow coordination among co-workers. And one thing that is also important is, the emotional intelligence of an employee is a determining factor for the success of performance, because in emotional intelligence an employee is able to control all his egos and desires and is able to understand other people or co-workers so as to create a dynamic work group atmosphere (Mudali 2003).

Every job in addition to requiring social competence and emotional intelligence, also requires self-motivation of employees, so that the work can be successful. Work motivation reflects employee behaviour at work. Work motivation relates to the extent to which an employee wants or is willing to try to achieve good performance. To move employees to conform to what the organization wants, it is necessary to understand the goals of employees working and the actions that will be taken to achieve these goals. Robbins and Timothy (2008) say that one form of expression of low work motivation is employee absenteeism. The high percentage of absenteeism and employee behaviour that is not in line with company expectations reflects a lack of employee motivation.

Social Competence

Social competence consists of the word's competence and social. Generally, competence in the large dictionary of languages

optimal work and capable exploiting potential resources human owned by employees to create company goals and

organization, so that it will make a positive contribution to organizational development. Other than that, Organizations need to pay attention to various factors that can affect motivation employees, in this case it is necessary to have the role of the organization in improving social competence, emotional intelligence, and work motivation to encourage passion and professional action in completing the work accordingly with fields and responsibilities each. Ladd (Jennifer, 2015) explains that social competence refers to the social, emotional, and cognitive skills and behaviours needed by individuals for successful adaptation to the social environment. For employees, behaviour that shows social competence revolves around work that establishes positive bonds and self-regulations while interacting with co-workers. In the theoretical view of social competence, there are two measurement focuses, namely on self or others, in this case measuring the success of employees in meeting personal goals or interpersonal relationships. Krasnor (Ren, 2015) suggests that social competence has 2 dimensions: 1) Interpersonal Problem Solving that relates to individuals being able to solve social problems they face in social interactions. Individuals are required to be able to solve interpersonal problems adaptively, where in finding solutions to problems individuals must choose goals and strategies. 2) Social Engagement that relates to the ability of individuals to be positively involved in interacting with other individuals. Based on this dimension, individuals must be able to participate in activities that involve other individuals.

Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman in Nurita (2012) "Emotional Intelligence is an emotional skill which includes the ability to control oneself and have endurance when facing obstacles, able to control impulses and not feel satisfied quickly, able to regulate moods and be able to manage anxiety so as not to interfere with thinking skills, able to empathize and hope". People who have high emotional intelligence will be able to understand themselves and the emotions of others. The person can use this understanding to improve his behaviour and attitude in a more positive direction, so that he is able to control his emotions, be more motivated, feel satisfied and be able to overcome problems with his work environment and life (Wong et al., 2015). Titimaea in Efendi and Sutanto (2013) reveals five dimensions of emotional intelligence: 1) self-awareness, a person's ability to understand various potentials within himself regarding his strengths and weaknesses. 2) self-regulation, a person's ability to control or control his emotions. 3) self-motivation, the ability to motivate yourself. 4) social awareness, the ability to recognize the emotions of others and 5) social skills, the ability to establish social relationships.

Work motivation

Motivation according to Munandar (2014) is "a process where needs encourage a person to carry out a series of activities that lead to the achievement of certain goals. When the needs have been met, a satisfaction will be achieved. A group of needs that have not been satisfied will cause tension, so it is necessary to carry out a series of activities to seek the achievement of specific goals that can satisfy the group of needs, so that tension is reduced. Malay S.P. Hasibuan (2015) states that work motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively, and are integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Meanwhile, according to T. Hani Handoko (2013) suggests that "motivation is a person's personal condition that encourages the individual's desire to carry out certain activities in order to achieve goals".

Fig.1 Research Framework

II. Method

This research uses the method of causal analysis. Causal analysis is a relationship that is causal in nature. Research conducted to determine the effect of one or more independent variables (independent variables) on the dependent variable (dependent variable). Independent variables are variables that affect or cause change or the emergence of the dependent variable (dependent) The dependent variable is the variable that is influenced or becomes the result of the independent variable (Sugiyono, 2014). The technique in this research is by distributing questionnaires to construction companies in Jakarta. The questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to be answered later (Sugiyono 2017). Data analysis using IBM SPSS for Descriptive analysis and hypothesis testing using smartPLS.

III. Result

Descriptive Respondent

Based on the results of data processing, most respondents in this study were aged 30-34, as many as 36 respondents or 39.1%. In terms of gender, most respondents were male as many as 49 respondents or 53.3%. In terms of education, most employees are graduates of as many as bachelors, 50 respondents or 54.3%. This is because to carry out architectural activities requires highly skilled personnel with the aim of obtaining the results expected by the Company. In terms of length of work, most respondents have only worked for 1-3 years as many as 48 Respondents or 52.2%.

Measurement Model

Analysis of the outer model is carried out to ensure that the measurements used are valid and reliable.

A. Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity testing is tested from each construct indicator. According to Ghazali (2015), an indicator is said to be valid if the value is greater than 0.70, while the loading factor of 0.50 to 0.60 can be considered sufficient. Based on these criteria, if there is a loading factor below 0.50 it will drop from the model.

Table 1. Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loadings	Description
Social Competence	KS1	0.128	Not Valid
	KS2	0.846	Valid
	KS3	0.797	Valid
	KS4	0.827	Valid
Emotional Intelligence	KE1	0.856	Valid
	KE2	0.215	Not Valid
	KE3	0.883	Valid
	KE4	0.725	Valid
	KE5	0.754	Valid
	KE6	0.143	Not Valid
	KE7	0.731	Valid
Work motivation	KE8	0.815	Valid
	MK1	0.792	Valid
	MK2	0.654	Valid
	MK3	0.640	Valid
	MK4	0.802	Valid
	MK5	0.309	Not Valid
	MK6	0.784	Valid
	MK7	0.830	Valid
	MK8	0.328	Not Valid
	MK9	0.679	Valid
	MK10	0.311	Not Valid
Employee Performance	MK11	0.242	Not Valid
	K1	0.194	Not Valid
	K2	0.726	Valid
	K3	0.218	Not Valid
	K4	0.247	Not Valid
	K5	0.769	Valid
	K6	0.810	Valid
	K7	0.768	Valid
	K8	0.822	Valid
	K9	0.690	Valid
	K10	0.891	Valid
	K11	0.243	Not Valid
K12	0.246	Not Valid	

Based on the data above, social competence in the KS1 indicator with the dimension of "interpersonal problem solving" is not that of KS so there are several indicators that must be removed from the dimensional model. In the emotional intelligence variable in the KE2 indicator with the dimension of "managing emotions", the KE6 indicator with the dimension "Recognizing other people's emotions" is not from KE so there are several indicators that must be removed from the dimensional model. In the work motivation variable, there are two indicators, namely MK5 and MK8 with the dimension of "need for affiliation" which is not from the Constitutional Court so that there are several indicators that must be removed from the dimensional model, there are two indicators MK10 and MK11 with the dimension of "need for power". In the employee performance variable in the K1 indicator with the dimension "quality of work" is not from the KK so there are several indicators that must be removed from the dimensional model, there are two indicators of K3 and K4 with the dimension of "work quantity" which is not from the KK so there are several indicators that must be removed. it is omitted from the dimension model, and the indicator K11 with the dimension of "independence" KK 12 with the dimension of "work commitment" is not from the KK so that there are several indicators that must be removed from the dimension model. The following are the results of the elimination of indicators and calculations grouped according to dimensions:

Table 2. Convergent Validity (Modification)

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loadings	Description
Social Competence	KS2	0.846	Valid
	KS3	0.797	Valid
	KS4	0.827	Valid
Emotional Intelligence	KE1	0.856	Valid
	KE3	0.883	Valid
	KE4	0.725	Valid
	KE5	0.754	Valid
	KE7	0.731	Valid
	KE8	0.815	Valid
Work motivation	MK1	0.792	Valid
	MK2	0.654	Valid
	MK3	0.640	Valid
	MK4	0.802	Valid
	MK6	0.784	Valid
	MK7	0.830	Valid
Employee Performance	MK9	0.679	Valid
	K2	0.726	Valid
	K5	0.769	Valid
	K6	0.810	Valid
	K7	0.768	Valid
	K8	0.822	Valid
	K9	0.690	Valid
	K10	0.891	Valid

The results of the modification of the convergent validity test in Table above shows that all indicators have met the convergent validity because they have a loading factor value above 0.50.

B. Discriminant Validity

Due to the absence of a convergent validity problem, the next step tested is a problem related to discriminant validity. In discriminant validity testing, reflective indicators can be seen in the cross loading between the indicator and the construct. An indicator is declared valid if it has a loading factor for other constructs. Thus, latent constructs predict indicators in their block better than indicators in other blocks. The following below are the results of the Discriminant Validity test with indicators and dimensions:

Table 3. Convergent Validity (Modification)

	Emotional Intelligence	Employee Performance	Social Competence	Work motivation
K10	0.772	0.894	0.762	0.804
K2	0.602	0.716	0.593	0.593
K5	0.707	0.769	0.579	0.698
K6	0.672	0.820	0.671	0.674
K7	0.680	0.788	0.619	0.619
K8	0.690	0.832	0.672	0.672
K9	0.629	0.684	0.554	0.636

KE1	0.858	0.735	0.703	0.695
KE3	0.885	0.850	0.841	0.835
KE4	0.727	0.631	0.608	0.571
KE5	0.761	0.620	0.605	0.649
KE7	0.731	0.599	0.451	0.568
KE8	0.811	0.657	0.605	0.632
KS2	0.649	0.731	0.850	0.767
KS3	0.729	0.632	0.811	0.630
KS4	0.637	0.640	0.821	0.672
MK1	0.703	0.714	0.688	0.811
MK2	0.572	0.550	0.500	0.642
MK3	0.546	0.511	0.524	0.675
MK4	0.648	0.669	0.745	0.809
MK6	0.725	0.739	0.714	0.812
MK7	0.663	0.722	0.701	0.823
MK9	0.515	0.559	0.490	0.684

From the table above, the loading of the Social Competency Factor with its indicators is higher than the loading of the KS indicator factor with other constructs. Then the loading of the Emotional Intelligence Factor with its indicators is higher than the loading of the KE indicator factor with other constructs. Then the loading of the Work Motivation Factor is higher than the loading of the MK indicator factor with other constructs. And the loading of Employee Performance Factors is higher than the loading of KK indicator factors with other constructs. This shows that latent constructs predict indicators in their block better than indicators in other blocks. From the results of the cross-loading analysis, it appears that there is no problem with discriminant validity.

Next is to compare the correlation between variables with the AVE root. The measurement model has good discriminant validity if the AVE of each variable is greater than the correlation between variables. The AVE value can be seen from the Fornell-Larcker Criterion Smart PLS 3.0 output which is presented in table below:

Table 4. Discriminant Validity (FornellLarcker Criterion)

Variable	Emotional Intelligence	Employee Performance	Social Competence	Work motivation
Emotional Intelligence	0.798			
Employee Performance	0.501	0.729		
Social Competence	0.465	0.524	0.828	
Work motivation	0.178	0.681	0.259	0.754

The FornellLarcker Criterion Correlation value of social competence is 0.828 higher than the correlation between employee performance constructs. Emotional intelligence is 0.798 higher than the correlation of the construct of work motivation and employee performance. Social Competence 0.828 is higher than work motivation, intelligence, and employee performance. Thus, it can be concluded that all the constructs in the estimated model meet the criteria for discriminant validity.

C. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Table 5. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)
Emotional Intelligence	0.637
Employee Performance	0.622
Social Competence	0.685
Work motivation	0.569

From the table above the test results with the AVE value show that all constructs have potential reliability to be tested further. This is because the AVE value on emotional intelligence, social competence, work motivation and employee performance has been greater than 0.50

D. Composite Reliability dan Cronbach’s Alpha

Table 6. Composite Reliability dan Cronbach’s Alpha

Variable	Composite Reability	Cronbach’s Alpha	Description
Emotional Intelligence	0.913	0.884	Reliable
Employee Performance	0.920	0.897	Reliable
Social Competence	0.867	0.771	Reliable
Work motivation	0.902	0.872	Reliable

Structural Model

After the estimated model meets the Outer Model criteria, the next step is testing the structural model (Inner Model). Inner model testing is the development of concept and theory-based models to analyze the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables that have been described in a conceptual framework. The testing phase of the structural model (inner model) is carried out by the following steps.

A. R-Square (R²)

Table 6.R-Square (R²)

Variable	R-Square (R ²)	R-Square Adjusted
Employee Performance	0,811	0,804

From the data above it can be concluded that the influence model of the independent latent variables of Social Competence, Emotional Intelligence, and Work Motivation provides an R-Square (R²) value of 0.811 and it is interpreted that the variability of the Employee Performance construct can be explained by the variables of social competence, emotional intelligence, and Work motivation is 81.1% while 18.9% is explained by other variables not examined in this model.

B. Q-Square (Goodness of Fit Model)

Testing the Goodness of Fit structural model on the inner model uses the predictive relevance (Q²) value. Q-Square value greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has a predictive relevance value. The R-Square value of each endogenous variable in this study can be seen in the following calculations:

The predictive relevance value is obtained by the formula:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2_1)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.811)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0.189$$

$$Q^2 = 0.811$$

The results of the above calculations show the predictive relevance value of 0.811 is greater than 0 (zero). This means that 81.1% of the variation in employee performance (dependent variable) is explained by the variables used, thus the model is said to be feasible to have a relevant predictive value.

C. Path Coefficient

The significance of the estimated parameters provides very useful information about the relationship between the research variables. The basis used in testing the hypothesis is the value contained in the output result for inner weight. This test is carried out based on the results of data processing that has been carried out using the PLS (Partial Least Square) program. The results of this test will show whether all the analysed paths show significant results as seen from the results of the Original Sample and its t-statistics. To test the proposed hypothesis, it can be seen the value of the t-statistic. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is +1.96, which if the t value is in the range of -1.96 and 1.96 values, the hypothesis will be rejected or in other words accept the null hypothesis (H0). The estimation

results of t-statistics can be seen in the path coefficient (t-statistics).

Table 7. Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sampel (O)	Sampel Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
Emotional Intelligence → Employee Performance	0.278	0.267	0.133	2.083	0.038	Positive - Significant
Social Competence → Employee Performance	0.379	0.372	0.163	2.328	0.020	Positive - Significant
Work motivation → Employee Performance	0.299	0.322	0.123	2.441	0.015	Positive - Significant

Based on the table above, it shows:

1. The Influence of Social Competence on Employee Performance
Based on the first hypothesis test (H₁) in this study, the results showed that Social Competence had an effect on Employee Performance. Because T statistic > T table (2.328 > 1.96) and the hypothesis was accepted.
2. Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance Based on the second hypothesis test (H₂) in this study, the results showed that Emotional Intelligence had an effect on employee performance. Because T statistic > T table (2.083 > 1.96) and the hypothesis is accepted.
3. The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance
Based on the third hypothesis test (H₃) in this study, the results showed that work motivation had an effect on employee performance. Because T statistic > T table (2.441 > 1.96) and the hypothesis is accepted

Fig. 2 Bootstrapping Test Results

IV. Discussion

Based on the results of the PLS (Partial Least Square) analysis, this section will discuss the results of the calculations that have been carried out. Testing is shown through existing hypotheses so that we can find out how each variable affects the other variables.

The Influence of Social Competence on Employee Performance

The results of the study found that social competence influences employee performance. This means that the better the social competence possessed by an employee, the closer the relationship will be between fellow colleagues, and will affect the performance generated by the employee. The dimension considered to be the most influencing according to respondents is the dimension of "Interpersonal Problem Solving" and it can be analysed that 92 respondents, the majority of whom are male, feel that the ability to solve problems due to their desires and interests can affect better performance.

Because it is well known that in a service company engaged in construction, conflicts between employees are very likely to occur for certain reasons. So, an employee who has a high desire to solve interpersonal problems is considered to have an even better effect on performance. There are most employees who have only worked for 1 - 3 years who are categorized as new by researchers. So, with this, employees should have good social competence to maintain and strengthen relationships between employees, both new employees and old employees.

The results of this study support the previous research conducted by Winanti (2015) "The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance", where there is a Social Competency variable that has a positive effect on Employee Performance. And, by Sahentuk (2014) "The Influence of Intellectual, Social, Spiritual Competence on Employee Performance" where the Social Competence variable has a positive effect on Employee Performance. This indicates that how important it is for employees to have good social competence to create a peaceful and peaceful work environment, so that employee performance will increase.

The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance

The results of the study found that emotional intelligence has an effect on employee performance. This means that accepting the actions taken by the organization and being able to control, manage and respect the emotions of oneself or others will make employees feel calm and have no burden when doing work and the resulting performance will also increase. And will increasingly appreciate a relationship that exists between fellow employees in any position.

Dimension that is rated by the highest respondent is the dimension "Managing self-emotions & self-motivating". With most employees who have worked for a long time between 1 - 3 years, researchers are categorized as new. So, it can be analysed that the way employees manage emotions and can motivate themselves are very important things for an employee to have to improve their performance. Because basically in construction companies there are usually employees who find it difficult to control their emotions and lack enthusiasm at work or tend to be lazy to run a project. So, employees who can control their emotions well are expected to be able to produce good performance as well. And most employees of construction company who are engaged in building construction are aged 30-34 years. So, employees at that age should already have good emotional intelligence because they have passed and faced any things / obstacles. And the dimension that is the lowest factor is the dimension of "Recognizing Self Emotions" / can be interpreted as someone who is aware and able to overcome their strengths and weaknesses, where for some employees it is not the main thing to have good emotional intelligence, where some Most of the employees are male, and it can be analysed that some employees of construction company have not been able to recognize the potential, strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of these employees.

The results of this study support previous research conducted by Rahmasari (2012) "The Influence of Intellectual Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, and Spiritual Intelligence on Employee Performance." Where the Emotional Intelligence variable has a positive effect on employee performance and Setyaningrum (2016) "The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance (Study at PT Jasa Raharja)" where Emotional Intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance, PT Jasa Raharja itself is engaged in social insurance services.

The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

The results of the study found that work motivation has an effect on employee performance. This means that employees who feel that they are motivated by both internal and external factors will feel free and comfortable when carrying out the work given. Even though they are under work pressure, the higher the employee's motivation to work because it is driven by something that is to be achieved and is expected, this motivation can arouse employee morale and improve employee performance itself.

Dimension that is most influencing to improve employee performance is the dimension of the need for achievement. Which means that most construction company employees with educational status are Bachelor (S1). Having a desire to

get high achievement or make a good contribution to the company is what makes employees able to improve their performance. And in companies that are engaged in construction, the achievement that employees can achieve is by providing input to attract other people / other companies to cooperate with construction company to run joint projects or use the services of construction company is an achievement. which can lead to increased employee performance. And most employees who work at construction company smell work for 1-3 years where this can also be a trigger for employees to improve their performance to achieve the achievement goals that each employee wants to have and of course be a good contribution to construction company.

The results of this study support previous research conducted by Abidin (2016) "The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance" in which the Work Motivation Variable has a positive effect on Employee Performance. However, in research conducted by Surjosuseno (2015) "The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance (Study at UD. There is a Plastic Factory)" Where work motivation has no positive effect on employee performance, although the variables under study are the same. However, because the object of the company being examined is engaged in different fields and of course has different characteristics, the results obtained can be very different.

V. Conclusion

This research is intended to determine the effect of social competence, emotional intelligence, and motivation on employee performance on Construction Company in Jakarta, Indonesia. Based on the data analysis and discussion stated in the previous chapter, several research conclusions can be stated as follows:

1. Social competence has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of construction company. So, it can be concluded that the better the social competence that is created in the work environment, the better the employee's performance, and vice versa, the worse the competence, the worse the employee's performance. So, it can be concluded in this study that the higher the employee has the social competence to create a harmonious and peaceful work environment, the employee's performance will increase.
2. Emotional Intelligence has a positive effect on the performance of employees of construction company. So, it can be concluded that the better the emotional intelligence that is created, the better the employee's performance and vice versa, the worse the emotional intelligence, the worse the employee's performance. In the sense that construction company, employees feel that emotional intelligence / the ability to manage emotions is very important to improve employee performance.
3. Motivation has a positive effect on the performance of the employees of construction company. Hence, it can be concluded that the better the motivation created, the higher the employee's performance and vice versa, the worse the motivation, the worse the employee's performance. In this study it can be concluded that employees who have high motivation to do a job will result in better performance.

VI. Recommendation

Social Competence

Construction company must provide training to raise awareness of how important it is to establish and maintain relationships with other colleagues, by holding a "Family Gathering" which will make the relationship between fellow employees even better. Social Competence owned by employees must be improved in its role to explain and tie the targets that must be achieved by employees, and the lack of giving freedom of opinion for employees in decision making. The time that the competence can use to run and improve targets is not only at the time of the briefing but can be done by conducting open discussions so that the search for solutions to achieve the target can be carried out simultaneously.

Emotional Intelligence

Construction company must pay attention to conflicts that occur within the scope of workers, both in the field or in the work environment of the operational office, by adding a job desk for the HR team to pay attention to what phenomena are happening in the employee environment and guaranteeing employees so as not to always be in big conflict. Future research should use a more recent assessment of emotional intelligence or use an assessment of emotional intelligence based on other researchers apart from Goleman to see the flexibility of the effect of emotional intelligence on performance if different measures are used.

Motivation

Construction company must hold activities or training to increase work motivation of its employees so that they do not feel stalled in the abilities that the employee already has, it can be by providing workshops for employees even though they are already competent in that field. Employee work motivation is less influenced by their desire to get awards and

work performance. Not only with incentives to increase employee motivation. Companies can provide motivation with a clear career path and hold family gathering events which are held twice a year.

The researcher realizes that there are still many shortcomings and limitations of information in this study, therefore, in connection with this, the researcher suggests for further researchers who will conduct research with related variables contained in this study, namely Social Competence, Emotional Intelligence and Motivation towards employee performance so that further research can develop other variables such as organizational culture and workload so that it can be used as a reference for researching variables that have never been done or using other research objects and with the addition of the number of respondents to different research objects. So that further research will be more perfect and provide more information.

REFERENCE

- [1.] Agung, I. (2014). Kajian Kompetensi Kepribadian dan Sosial. In *Jurnal Ilmiah VISI P2TK PAUDNI - Vol. 9, No.2* (pp. 83 - 93). Puslitjak Balitbang Kemendikbud.
- [2.] Busro, M. (2018). *Teori Teori Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- [3.] Dr. Muhammad, B. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- [4.] Gio, P. U., & Elly, R. (2016). *Belajar Olah Data dengan SPSS, Minitab, R, Microsoft Excel, Eviews, LISREL, AMOS, dan SmartPLS*. Medan: Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- [5.] Goleman, D. (2016). *Emotional Intelligence*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [6.] Hamdan, S. R. (2017). Kecerdasan Emosional dalam Al - Qur'an. *Schema: Journal of Psychological Research*, 35 - 45.
- [7.] Hasibuan, M. S., & Fauzi, I. A. (2007). *Definisi Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Aspek Kuantitatif Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT Alex Media Komputindo.
- [8.] Herujito, Y. (2015). *Dasar Dasar Manajemen*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- [9.] HM, E. M. (2016). Mengelola Kecerdasan Emosi. *Tadrib 2.2*, 198 - 213.
- [10.] I, G. (2008). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [11.] I, G. (2014). *Structural Equating Modeling, Metode Alternatif Dengan Partial Least Square (PLS) Edisi 4*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [12.] Jaya, M. K., Mulyadi, D., & Sulaeman, E. (2012). Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Kantor Kementerian Agama Kabupaten Karawang. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 1039 - 1048.
- [13.] Kaswan. (2012). *MSDM Untuk Keunggulan Bersaing Organisasi*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- [14.] Larasati, S., & Alini, G. (2014). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Wilayah Telkom Jabar (Jakarta Barat) Utara (Witel Bekasi). *Jurnal Manajemen dan Organisasi*, 200 - 213.
- [15.] Mardiana, I. N. (2018). Analisis Pengaruh Kompetensi Intelektual, Emosional dan Sosial Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Peta Ilmu 5.1*.
- [16.] Mellahi, K., Collings, D. G., & Cascio, W. F. (2017). *The Oxford Handbook Of Talent Mnsngement*. United Kingdom: Oxford University CPI Group.
- [17.] Prihartanta, W. (2015). *Teori teori Motivasi*. Banda Aceh: Jurnal Adabiya, Vol. 1 No. 83.
- [18.] Prof. Dr. H.M. Burhan Bungin, S. (2005). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif*. Jakarta, Indonesia: KENCANA.
- [19.] Risma, D. (2012). Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan : Penelitian Eksperimen. *Jurnal Educhild : Pendidikan dan Sosial 1.1*, 86 - 97.
- [20.] Setiawan, K. C. (2015). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan level pelaksana di divisi operasi PT. Pusri Palembang. *Psikis : Jurnal Psikologi Islam 1.2*, 42 - 53.
- [21.] Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. PT Alfabet.

- [22.] Susanty, A., & Baskoro, S. W. (2013). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Disiplin Kerja Serta Dampaknya Pada Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Kasus Pada Pt. Pln (Persero) Apd Semarang). *Jurnal Teknik Industri*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 77-84.
- [23.] Theodora, O. (2015). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Sejahtera Motor Gemilang. *Agora* 3.2, 187 - 195.
- [24.] Trihandini, & Meirnayati, R. F. (2005). Analisis Pengaruh Kecerdasan Intelektual, Kecerdasan Emosional, Dan Kecerdasan Spiritual Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Kasus Pada Hotel Horison). *Jurnal Manajemen* 2015, Karawang.
- [25.] Verayanti, P. D., Nuridja, M., & Indrayani, L. (2014). Pengaruh Kompetensi Sosial Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Jurnal UPG Vol: 4, No : 1, 40 - 52*.
- [26.] Wibowo, C. T. (2015). Analisis Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional (EQ) dan Kecerdasan Spiritual (SQ) Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 1 - 16.
- [27.] Winanti, M. B. (2012). *Pengaruh Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan* . Jawa Barat: Majalah Ilmiah UNIKOM Vol. 7, No.2 .